

APPENDIX

A. Correlation Effectiveness across Multiple Datasets

Figures 7a-7e show RevealNet’s correlation effectiveness on additional datasets from Fu et al. [29], showing similar trends to those discussed in Section V on bitcoinminer.

The TPR and FPR obtained across all datasets indicate that using the integer sketch by Coskun [11] achieves performance similar to TAM, while requiring 10% to 60% less memory (see Figure 5). This suggests that sketching can be effective for reducing memory usage. The results also show that the binary sketch by Coskun et al. [11] achieves higher TPR than TAM in some cases, but with a higher FPR. Both sketches by Nasr et al. [9] perform either similarly to or worse than Coskun’s sketches. These findings further support the claim made in Section V that sketches can be used to reduce memory and computation costs while maintaining comparable performance.



(a) adload



(b) drindex



(c) oracle



(d) penetho



(e) snojan

Fig. 7: Correlation effectiveness of RevealNet across multiple datasets.